

CELEBRATING 30 YEARS OF THE NATIONAL RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT INSTITUTE FOR MARINE GEOLOGY AND GEO-ECOLOGY – GEOECOMAR ACTIVITY

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10254284

In November 2023, the National Institute of Marine Geology and Geo-ecology (GeoEcoMar) celebrated 30 years of research in the macro-geosystem Danube-Danube Delta-coastal area-Black Sea.

The activity of the research entity started in 1993, when the Laboratory of Sedimentology and Marine Geology separated from the Institute of Geology and Geophysics of Romania and became the Romanian Center for Marine Geology and Geo-ecology, embarking on a survival adventure, further development and the fulfillment of the scientific and socio-economic objectives that were entrusted.

Which are these?

The seas and oceans, which cover over 70% of the surface of our blue planet, are becoming more and more important both in maintaining an environmental and climatic balance favorable for life on Earth, and as a practically inexhaustible reserve of natural mineral and biological resources for mankind.

Here, new conventional and non-conventional energy resources, new sources of raw materials indispensable for the further development of the world economy are discovered. Important progress is registered in the field of technologies intended for research, exploration and exploitation of these resources, and the international legislative framework that governs these activities is perfected for the International Seabed Zone, but also for the exclusive economic zones of the riparian countries. These premises are created to attract marine resources in the world economic circuit and allowing us to foresee new developments and resolutions of the economy, new changes in the international economic and geo-political balance, a new world covering the interests of the countries around the globe.

Countries who are having the chance to be riparian of a sea or ocean and are not paying attention to this relatively

new research scientific field for sustainable exploitation of marine resources are considerably diminishing their chances of having a prosperous and continuously developing economy.

On the other hand, maintaining the environmental balance of the hydrosphere has become a priority problem for humanity. The recent rapid global changes, determined by natural and, above all, anthropogenic causes, must be studied, understood and measures need to be taken for reducing their effects and ensuring general adaptation to these new conditions which are constantly evolving.

In the situation of closed or semi-closed seas, such as the Black Sea, the problems become even more pressing and imperious. Here, the influences of the great rivers intervene even with a greater extent on the environmental conditions and the dynamics of sea water masses, but also on life directly. Even more so, things are getting complicated by the importance and influences that the international geopolitical situation acquires in these intracontinental seas.

Those are the multitude and complexity of the issues that have been met before the Romanian Center for Marine Geology and Geo-ecology and still represent a great importance for the world scientific community, in which GeoEcoMar is involved.

The Center took root and developed quite quickly, so that in three years the qualification criteria as a national institute were met and thus, in 1996, the Center turned into the National Research-Development Institute for Marine Geology and Geo-ecology – GeoEcoMar (NIRD GeoEcoMar). This year, after three decades of activity and success, which have already passed, we appreciate the results of the national and international importance of the GeoEcoMar institute.

The international conference, organized by NIRD GeoEcoMar in November 2023, in collaboration with the Romanian Academy, on the topic of Recent and Ancient River-

Delta-Sea systems was intended to publicize the contribution researchers in this field, by deciphering part of the exposed problems.

The contribution of the entire institute is wide and varied, being published in various significant international journals, including our annual scientific journal – *Geo-Eco-Marina* (which is open-accessible, published mainly online with an international wide circulation, being also SCOPUS-indexed).

Geo-Eco-Marina is 1 year younger than the institute and we hope to celebrate its 30 years anniversary in 2024.

Following the celebration of 30 years of research in the macro-geosystem Danube-Danube Delta-coastal area-Black Sea, I wish GeoEcoMar NIRD a long term-activity with many successes, and to its entire scientific community many achievements and perseverance in its so beautiful and noble work.

Academician **Nicolae Panin**